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KRIZIA ANNE S. ESTRELLA

**COP OR DROP: AN ANALYSIS OF THE INFLUENCE OF SOCIAL MEDIA
MARKETING ON SNEAKERHEADS' ATTITUDES AND PERCEPTIONS AMONG
RESELLERS AND CONSUMERS OF RHAND RHELLE**

Thesis Adviser:

DR. EMELY M. AMOLOZA
Faculty of Information and Communication Studies

09 August 2023

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This paper was prepared by **KRIZIA ANNE S. ESTRELLA** with the title: “**COP OR DROP: AN ANALYSIS OF THE INFLUENCE OF SOCIAL MEDIA MARKETING ON SNEAKERHEADS’ ATTITUDES AND PERCEPTIONS AMONG RESELLERS AND CONSUMERS OF RHAND RHELLE**” is hereby accepted by the Faculty of Information and Communication Studies, U.P. Open University, in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the degree Course.

DR. EMELY M. AMOLOZA
Adviser

09 August 2023
(Date)

DR. EMELY M. AMOLOZA
Program Chair

09 August 2023
(Date)

DR. DIEGO S. MARANAN
Dean
Faculty of Information and Communication Studies

09 August 2023
(Date)

Biographical Sketch

Krizia Anne S. Estrella is an undergraduate student pursuing a Bachelor of Arts degree in Multimedia Studies at the University of the Philippines Open University. She was born in Quezon City, Philippines, on April 24, 1999. During her junior high years, she attended Quezon City Science High School. She graduated senior high school in Claret School of Quezon City, where she made history as the first female batch valedictorian and the first female student council officer.

Throughout her undergraduate years, Krizia has immersed herself in the study of multimedia. She has taken various courses and developed a thorough understanding of subjects like Multimedia and Society and Multimedia and Popular Culture. In order to increase her knowledge in the field, she also actively participated in the 5th Online Digital Marketing Course offered by the University of the Philippines Institute for Small-Scale Industries. These experiences have sharpened her research skills, deepened her understanding of multimedia, and provided her with practical insights into the methodologies and practices employed in the field.

The culmination of Krizia's undergraduate journey is her thesis, "Cop or Drop: An Analysis of the Influence of Social Media Marketing on Sneakerheads' Attitudes and Perceptions Among Resellers and Consumers of Rhand Rhelle." This thesis exemplifies her commitment to investigating and exploring social media's influence on marketing in today's digital age. By undertaking this research, she aims to contribute new insights and knowledge to multimedia, particularly in social media marketing. Looking ahead, Krizia is committed to continuing her academic and professional growth in multimedia. She envisions pursuing further education and engaging in research opportunities that allow her to make meaningful contributions and impact in the field.

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Abstract

The rise of e-commerce became a promising phenomenon that gave opportunity among numerous sneaker business owners, especially in social media. However, regardless of the rapid growth of the shoe market, there are limited studies illustrating consumer behavior, especially among sneakerheads. Therefore, the researcher was driven to analyze how social media marketing influences the attitudes and perceptions of sneakerheads. In addition, the study attempted to modify the research objectives of Gibson's (2018) study to be more suitable in the context of the sneaker market. Thus, the researcher utilized a quantitative-descriptive research design to suffice the mentioned objectives. In addition, the researcher surveyed 120 consumers of Rhand Rhelle, a sneaker store in Metro Manila. Then, the gathered data were further analyzed through descriptive statistics and presented with tables and figures. Finally, the findings revealed that sneakerheads have a positive attitude towards social media, considering their patronage and engagement on it. In addition, sneakerheads perceive social media marketing as an important tool to acquire customer loyalty, increased profits, and widen audience reach. However, sneaker stores shall consider the type of content they post as it was the most important factor perceived by the respondents that are significant for businesses like them. Further, the researcher concluded that social media marketing can influence the attitudes and perceptions of sneakerheads. With this being the case, the researcher gave recommendations that can be utilized by sneaker business owners as a compass for potential strategies and programs.

Keywords: *Sneakerheads, Shoes, Social Media Marketing, Social Media, Business*

I. INTRODUCTION

Rationale

Social media as a marketing platform has become a growing trend in the past years, where 91% of marketers and 96% of small business owners use it as a business tool (Schaffer, 2022). This phenomenon was perceived to be anchored to the fact that there are more than three (3) billion social media users as of 2021, which translates to a higher probability of reaching the target market of businesses (Porteous, 2021). Additionally, Cover (2021) revealed in their article that company executives have been highly dependent on social media in terms of gathering data or market research and in their decision-making. Thus, social media is becoming paramount to the business landscape, especially in marketing and advertising.

Social media marketing is a growing trend in which social media platforms, such as Facebook, are used to promote a certain company and its goods and services. This emerging trend enables businesses to quickly connect with their target consumers (Arsath, 2018). Initially, conventional marketing communication methods such as radio, television commercials, and print advertisements were highly valued mediums. Yet, social media marketing currently provides numerous options for businesses or brands to communicate with their target clients for free; the only cost is time (Roy, 2022).

Moreover, Almohaimmeed (2019) revealed in their study that social media marketing has a significant impact on both brand loyalty and customer purchase intention, making it critical for businesses to ensure an effective application of it and to consider its precedents, which would bring the advantages associated with social media marketing to light, affecting brand loyalty and customer buying behavior. Similarly, Jamil et al. (2022) revealed in their study that social media marketing has an

impact on consumer intentions. Also, it has a considerable impact on consumers' social identity, purchase and involvement decisions, loyalty, and satisfaction.

Meanwhile, Dolega et al. (2021) mentioned that the efficacy of social media marketing differs based on the complexity, cost, and brand status of the product or services of the enterprise. Therefore, if customers perceive negative impressions or data regarding the cost, ease of use, and reputation, there is a huge probability of adverse marketing outcomes. In addition, Jonas (2021) revealed that social media advertising could foster misleading information and negative feedback, which could put the business at great risk.

In the Philippine context, Calleja et al. (2019) revealed in their study that social media marketing could acquire the attention, interest, and desire of consumers, but the actual time for these individuals to purchase the advertised product or service may take a while. Nevertheless, 82 percent of the total population of Filipinos have usual media accounts, and the country ranked second worldwide in terms of the frequency and time spent by Filipinos on social media (Caparas, 2023).

Moving forward, the sneakers community in the Philippines is flourishing, and when a highly limited design hits the market, enthusiasts rush to shops or enter raffles to get first dibs on a pair. These individuals believe that person's shoes can transport them to many locations. In fact, it helped the late Henry Sy, a well-known business mogul in the country, expand their commercial empire. Since it was purchased due to a need, as a luxurious accessory, or as a valued property, it is projected to be a thrilling craze like this shoe fever, which is at its apex and will continue to rise enormously (Andas, 2021).

The primary customers of sneakers are called the *sneakerheads*, which Choi (2017) further refers to as persons who collect, trade, or admire sneakers, while

Matthews et al. (2021) said that the symbolic importance of sports, popular music, fashion-building, and the negotiation and performance of masculine social identities all contributed to the rise of the many sneakerheads. The Jordan brand was chosen as the finest example by academics. Jordan's brand identity became synonymous with the evolution of sneakerheads' ideal selves. Nonetheless, younger sneakerheads, such as millennials, construct their ideal selves by being open to numerous brand selections while still recognizing the historical importance inherent in the Jordan brand.

However, despite the shoe market's rapid growth, there are very few studies conducted on consumer behavior specific to sneakerheads. According to Choi et al. (2015), previous qualitative studies on sneakerheads mostly focused on the relationship between advertisement and consumer behavior. Regarding sneakerheads' growing societal significance, the researchers noted that there is still a void in the literature about their perceptions, motivations, decision-making process, purchasing motives, and consumption misbehaviors.

The data above illustrated how social media marketing has greatly transformed how businesses can have an impact on their customers' behavior when it comes to promoting material that engages and retrieves specific user data that helps communication resonate with consumers. Social media platforms' power comes from their unrivaled ability in the three key areas of marketing: connection, interaction, and customer data acquisition. There is currently a literature gap about the effects of this change in marketing on customer attitudes and perceptions, particularly among sneakerheads. Due to the effect of social media marketing, this study presented literature on the attitude and perceptions of sneakerheads. The research's conclusions may also be crucial in creating contemporary business models that incorporate consumer behavior.

Executive Summary

Social media became a popular platform for businesses, such as Rhand Rhelle. This business is a sneaker store located in Quezon City, Metro Manila. It has a Facebook page with numerous followers, which makes it a suitable target research subject, specifically its consumers. Considering that the study aimed to investigate social media marketing and its influence on the perception and attitudes of sneakerheads, the researcher partnered with the store for the conduct of the study.

Further, previously published literature and studies have been centering on social media marketing as it is an increasing phenomenon where social media sites like Facebook are utilized to advertise a particular business and its products and services. Consequently, businesses can instantly connect with their target customers courtesy of this new trend.

In addition, there are various business outcomes that are believed to be attributed to social media marketing. Specifically, in pursuit of gaining the advantages that come with social media marketing and its effect on customer loyalty and customer buying behavior, businesses must make sure that it is used strategically and take into consideration its precedence. Customers' intentions to make purchases and brand loyalty are both significantly impacted by social media marketing.

Moreover, investigating social media as a business platform in the Philippine context can be relatively interesting. Considering the Philippines is one of the countries that have a high frequency of social media utility, social media marketing can be complex.

However, the body of knowledge on how the change in marketing throughout the years has impacted customer attitudes and perceptions, especially among sneakerheads, is very limited. Consequently, the study provided data on sneakerhead

attitudes and perceptions as a result of social media marketing. The study's conclusions may be crucial for creating contemporary business models that take customer behavior into consideration.

Statement of the Problem

This study aimed to analyze the influence of social media marketing on sneakerheads' attitudes and perceptions. More particularly, this study attempts to answer the modified research questions in Gibson's (2018) study in the context of the sneaker market.

1. What are the attitudes and perceptions of sneakerheads regarding social media usage and social media marketing?
2. What are the significant factors that make social media marketing effective on sneakerheads, particularly on customer brand loyalty and purchase decisions?
3. How can sneaker businesses utilize social media to improve customer interaction?

Objectives of the Study

This study aimed to analyze the influence of social media marketing on sneakerheads' attitudes and perceptions. More particularly, this study attempts to suffice the modified objectives in Gibson's (2018) study in the context of the sneaker market. Specifically, this study would like to:

1. Determine the attitudes and perceptions of sneakerheads regarding social media usage and social media marketing;

2. Assess the significant factors in making social media marketing effective on sneakerheads, particularly on customer brand loyalty and purchase decisions; and
3. Identify how sneaker businesses can utilize social media to improve customer interaction.

Significance of the study

The study was a significant endeavor in the growth and development of adopting technology and innovation in marketing strategies in the business sector, considering that it analyzed the consumer's perception and attitude as impacted by social media marketing. This study can also benefit businesses venturing to see how social media marketing influences the attitudes and perceptions of consumers. Specifically, the conduct of this study was beneficial to the following entities:

For the Staff of Rhand Rhelle – This study's findings may equip the sneaker store's staff and owners with knowledge about how they influence their customers through their social media marketing strategy. Furthermore, the findings can uncover their business's positives and negatives, which they can utilize to develop strategies to enhance their strengths and address their weaknesses as a contribution to the organization.

For Business Owners – The findings of this study shall support not only sneaker businesses but other kinds of businesses as well in keeping up with the trends of the present generation, which could eventually lead to an increase in revenues. This study may also help explore the strengths and weaknesses of utilizing social media marketing in business, especially since the platform can reach massive audiences.

For Consumers – The data from this study shall provide consumers with knowledge about how social media marketing strategies of particular businesses influence their attitudes and perceptions in purchasing decisions and brand loyalty. Also, they will be able to be aware of how social media marketing strategies work in the business setting where they have their respective roles.

For Marketers – The results of this study can be helpful to marketers in creating more robust strategies and approaches in terms of social media marketing. They can also utilize the research findings in modifying their current strategies to be more suitable on the social media platform or with customers with the same demographic profile.

For the Students – The data from this study shall also equip students with new knowledge that they can apply to themselves, and that can further be explored in the future.

For the Future Researchers – This study generated additional information regarding the perception and attitude of consumers as impacted by social media marketing. Therefore, these intellectually interested individuals can utilize the data from this study to support the studies they may be conducting.

Scope and Limitations of the Study

This study's scope and limitations are the following:

1. The study shall only focus on the analysis of the influence of social media marketing on sneakerheads' attitudes and perceptions based on the research objectives of the study, namely:
 - a. The attitudes and perceptions of sneakerheads regarding social media usage and social media marketing;

- b. Significant factors in making social media marketing effective on sneakerheads, particularly on customer brand loyalty and purchase decisions;
 - c. And how sneaker businesses can utilize social media to improve customer interaction.
- 2. The data collection of this study was limited only to consumers and resellers of Rhand Rhelle aged 18 to 64.
- 3. The inclusion criteria of the consumers include (a) adults aged 18 to 64; (b) should have a social media account; (c) should have availed of product or services of Rhand Rhelle at least once; (d) should be aware of the social media platforms or accounts used by Rhand Rhelle; (e) should give their consent upon participating in the study. Therefore, any grounds violating these criteria will disqualify participants from participating in the study.
- 4. The study was undertaken from August 2022 to September 2023 under the supervision of the research adviser.
- 5. The primary data collection source came from the results of the online survey that the researcher shall prepare.
- 6. The researcher gave the same set of questionnaires to the respondents. These survey questionnaires were designed based on the study's research objectives.

II. REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Social media marketing is a developing trend of utilizing social media channels to promote particular products and services (Arsath, 2018). 60% of Filipino small business owners rely on technology, with 51% using social media and messaging apps to keep their revenues afloat during the COVID-19 pandemic (Aguinaldo, 2020). According to Gibson (2018), social media marketing positively affects business by offering beneficial opportunities regarding brand loyalty, brand recognition, and foot traffic.

With the rise of this contemporary commercial strategy comes the formation of a new target market – the sneakerheads. These sneakerheads collect, trade, or admire sneakers and can take on diverse roles as consumers and resellers (Choi, 2017). Despite the sneaker market's rapid development, there is still little research on the field. As Choi et al. (2015) reported, there is still a gap in the resources concerning sneakerheads' increasing social significance and consumer behavior.

Thus, this research aims to answer how social media marketing influences sneakerheads. In particular, this study intends to adopt the modified objectives of Gibson's (2018) study in the context of the sneaker market – the influence of social media on sneakerheads' attitudes and perceptions, purchasing decisions, and consumer loyalty and interaction.

Social Media Marketing

According to Arsath (2018), social media marketing is a developing trend of utilizing social media channels to promote a particular business and its products and services. This developing trend allows companies to reach out to their consumers easily. The author mentioned Facebook as a prominent example of a social media

platform that transformed the way businesses perceive advertising. Instead of directing potential and existing consumers to their website pages, some companies lead their customers to their social network pages to increase their reach.

Aside from operating as a platform to reach out to a larger number of consumers, social media marketing increases brand awareness. Perdue (2010) stated that the significance of brand awareness does not solely rely on immediate sales but also on customers recalling a company's product or service. The researcher also expressed that an innovative way to increase brand awareness is by hiring influencers and turning these individuals into brand ambassadors. This strategy can indirectly acquire prospective new customers in online communities and strengthen customer loyalty.

On the other hand, a study by Karimi & Naghibi (2015) explored how social media marketing can pose a threat to businesses. As mentioned by the researchers, social media marketing is tremendously time-consuming. This modern-day marketing technique might need several people, such as a team, to work on it daily to address consumers' feedback and complaints. Moreover, being active and producing daily content can boost the engagement statistics between the business's social media site and the consumers.

Studies on social media marketing are growing due to people being largely dependent on technology. However, there is still a lot to be understood about this phenomenon. As Stephen (2016) reported, existing knowledge and research regarding the influence of social media marketing on consumers have primarily focused on word-of-mouth, a form of marketing where people circulate information about the services and products a certain business offers (Subramanian, 2018). Therefore, Dwivedi et al. (2021) suggested developing a body of research focusing on

consumer behavior, such as the relationship between social media marketing and the customer's loyalty to the brand and its products.

Attitudes and Perceptions Towards Social Media Marketing

As social media marketing continues to advance as a marketing strategy for businesses, more and more studies have been reported regarding its relationship with consumers. A study by Jamil et al. (2022) proved that social media marketing influences consumers' intentions. The data in the study were gathered through an online questionnaire from experienced users of Facebook and Instagram in Pakistan. The researchers found that social media marketing significantly impacts consumers' social identification, purchase and participation decisions, continuance intention, and customer satisfaction. Moreover, through this study, the researchers were able to determine that social identification affects the relationship between social media marketing and customer satisfaction.

Jamil et al.'s (2022) findings were further supported by the study of Iblasi et al. (2016), which focused on investigating the influence of social media marketing on consumers' purchasing decisions. The researchers collected the data from Samsung customers through distributed questionnaires. The study indicated that social media sites are a high-yielding and proliferating platform for practicing e-marketing. The use of these sites affects the stages of consumers' purchasing decisions, particularly need recognition, information search, alternatives evaluation, purchase decision, and post-purchase behavior (Munthiu, 2009). Furthermore, the researchers suggested that Facebook, Twitter, and YouTube are the top choices that companies should consider in their marketing plans.

On another note, Ahmad & Khan (2017) identified the essential variables in consumers' attitude formation: perceived usefulness, reliability, and word-of-mouth quality. The researchers argued that reliability significantly impacts attitude formation, followed by perceived usefulness and word-of-mouth quality. The researchers encouraged companies to utilize social media marketing in their products and services. The brand's presence on social media sites is advantageous in gathering livelier virtual users, resulting in a higher chance of purchasing its products online.

Gibson's (2018) study encapsulated the overall idea of the relationship between social media marketing and consumers. According to the study's results, social media marketing positively affects businesses. It offers beneficial opportunities such as online exposure, brand awareness, consumer-to-seller communication, valuable feedback, and consumer purchasing behavior. The researcher concluded that social media marketing is advantageous in terms of brand loyalty, brand recognition, and foot traffic.

Sneakerheads: Resellers and Consumers

Choi (2017) defined *sneakerheads* as persons who collect, trade, or admire sneakers. These people can have mixed roles as consumers, collectors, and resellers. According to Matthews et al. (2021), the symbolic value of sports, popular music, the construction of fashion, and the negotiation and performance of masculine social identities influenced the rise of the many sneakerheads. The researchers identified the Jordan brand as the best example in this case. The brand identity of Jordan became identical to the development of the sneakerheads' ideal selves. Nevertheless, younger sneakerheads, such as the millennials, develop their ideal selves by being open to

diverse brand options while still holding space to acknowledge the historical value innate to the Jordan brand.

Sneakerheads as consumers are those who collect and buy shoes. Laitasalo's (2016) study stated that sneakerheads are "fanatical" about shoes, especially on limited edition releases. These people will take the risk of camping out in front of a store overnight in the hopes of copping a pair of sneakers as the store opens. Wu (2020) claimed that consumers and collectors often give special meanings to specific sneakers. For instance, the Air Jordan 12 "Flu Game" is memorable since it honors Michael Jordan's remarkable performance during the game, even if the player suffered from flu. As such, Jordan fans and sneaker enthusiasts are willing to pay hundreds of dollars due to the memory depicted in their collection.

Kenny & Cetin (2021) stated that resellers, in the context of sneaker culture, invest in the sneaker resale market for the sole purpose of maximizing profits. The market has become a valuable and profitable business that resellers engage in using computer-programmed bots. It is an automated hacking software that scans online stores to purchase the latest, in-demand pairs of sneakers (Corina & Vancea, 2020). Aside from utilizing sneaker bots, other resellers engage in the practice of "back-dooring," a phrase that refers to the act of hoarding stocks of sneakers in stores before the public release date (Servantes, 2021).

Despite the sneaker market's rapid development, there are still few research studies in the field. Choi et al. (2015) claimed that preceding qualitative research on sneakerheads mostly centered on the correlation between advertising and consumer behavior. The researchers mentioned that there is still a gap in the literature concerning sneakerheads' increasing social significance, such as their perceptions,

motivations, decision-making process, consumption motives, and consumption misbehaviors.

The growing body of literature regarding social media marketing, attitudes and perceptions towards social media marketing, and sneakerheads resellers and consumers were presented above. It was revealed that social media has grown as a platform for commerce, including the sneaker business. Research trends show how beneficial and efficient social media is as a marketing platform (Arsath, 2018; Perdue, 2010) given that it can reach many audiences (Stephen, 2016); however, it is undeniable that businesses are not only susceptible to advantages but also their adverse effect. It was also claimed that social media could also jeopardize businesses if it garnered negative consumer feedback, which can easily be accessed by other individuals (Karimi & Nagbihi, 2015).

In line with this, social media are revealed to have been influencing the purchase decisions of consumers (Jamil et al., 2022) and can foster the relationship between consumers and entrepreneurs. These individuals can be referred to as sneakerheads in the realm of the sneaker business. This sneaker market has grown over the years and has become in demand, primarily since sneakerheads are known as 'fanatics' of these goods.

Therefore, this study can generate information on whether social media marketing is beneficial for sneaker businesses, particularly Rhand Rhelle, and also determine how social media marketing may influence customer loyalty and purchase decisions. Also, it can be perceived above that there was a scarcity of studies regarding the role of social media marketing among sneakerheads in the local context. Thus, these gaps in the literature can potentially be filled through the conduct of the present study.

Theoretical Framework

The influence of social media marketing in the context of the sneaker market is still a matter that branches out to various vague concepts and interpretations if not directed and asserted in a specific manner. Therefore, the researcher used Marshall McLuhan's Media Theory as the foundation of the study. According to Pan & Crotts (2012), the theory argues that "the media itself, rather the actual content of the media, will transform people and society." This theory is also popularly quoted as "the media is the message." In this research, social media marketing has influenced consumers not because of the content it contains but because of the mode of communication it entails (Jacinto et al., 2021).

This theory is deemed suitable in the present study as it involves the role of the media in society. As the participants of this study are consumers and the subject matter involves a business, which both are part of the society, this theory encapsulates the study's significant variables, such as the business and its consumers.

Conceptual Framework

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

Figure 1 shows the conceptual framework of the study. The input includes the data needed to be gathered by the researcher, such as the demographic profile of the participants, the attitudes and perceptions of sneakerheads regarding social media usage and social media marketing, the significant factors in making social media marketing effective on sneakerheads, particularly on how social media influenced

sneakerheads' brand loyalty and purchase decisions, and how sneaker businesses utilize social media to improve customer interaction.

The process involved data gathering through an online survey based on the study's research objectives and statistical tools analysis, which involves descriptive statistics, such as weighted Mean, percentage, and Standard Deviation.

The output of the study includes valuable insights into the analysis of the influence of social media marketing on sneakerheads' attitudes and perceptions among resellers and consumers of Rhand Rhelle.

Operational Definition of Terms

- Brand Loyalty – This refers to a customer's behavior to continuously purchase a product from a specific trusted brand to which they are already committed.
- Consumer – In the sneaker market, this refers to an individual who consumes or purchases a sneaker for their own use or collection.
- Customer Interaction – This refers to the communication that occurs between a customer and a business, such as providing assistance through calls or chat messages on social media.
- Purchase Decision – This refers to the decision-making process that a consumer does before making a purchase. This evaluation process may include identifying a need, scanning through multiple product options, and choosing a particular brand.
- Reseller – In the sneaker market, this refers to an individual who purchases huge quantities of highly sought sneakers and sells them in order to make a profit.
- Sneakerhead – This refers to a person who can either be a collector, consumer, or reseller in the sneaker market. This individual can admire sneakers as a hobby, as a form of fashion statement, or for business purposes.

- Social Media Marketing – This form of digital marketing utilizes social media applications and networking services as a marketing tool in order to build a brand, interact with customers, increase sales, and for brand promotions.
- Social Media Usage – This refers to the length of time an individual spends on social media.

III. METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The researcher utilized a quantitative research approach, specifically a descriptive research design, to determine the influence of social media marketing on sneakerheads' attitudes and perceptions.

Quantitative research focuses on generating knowledge and creating an understanding of the social world (Burrell & Gross, 2017). The researcher would like to be more specific and use a specific type of research that aims to gather data without manipulating the variables. According to Gray et al. (2017, p. 334), descriptive research aims to develop theories, classify emerging phenomena, and primarily answer the “what” or “how much” questions. Furthermore, descriptive research is a method that allows the researcher to measure actual behavior that is used to describe characteristics or functions (Fluet, 2021). Descriptive research aims to describe a population, situation, or specific phenomenon systematically. Moreover, this research design utilizes a wide variety of research methods to explore or investigate the variable/s of the study (McCombes, 2019).

Hence, the researcher chose this research design as this study involved numerical data and aimed to identify characteristics, frequencies, categories, and trends without manipulating variables and testing the significance of relationships. The

researcher conducted the study based on two variables: social media marketing and attitudes and perceptions of sneakerheads. The study also determined how social media marketing affects the purchasing decisions of sneakerheads and identified how sneaker businesses utilize social media to improve customer interaction.

Locale of the Study

The data collection of this study was undertaken in Quezon City, Philippines, from February 2023 to May 2023 under the supervision of the research adviser. Specifically, it was conducted at Rhand Rhelle, located on the Ground Floor of Gateway Mall General Malvar Avenue, Araneta City, Cubao, Quezon City, 1109 Metro Manila, Philippines.

Figure 2. Research Locale

Respondents of the Study

The study was comprised of one hundred (100) participants who are resellers and consumers of Rhand Rhelle – a sneaker and hype streetwear store located in Quezon City, Philippines. The researcher reached out to Rhand Rhelle through their Instagram account. These participants passed the inclusion criteria, which are as follows:

1. Adults aged 18 to 64;
2. Should have a social media account;
3. Should have availed of product or services of Rhand Rhelle at least once;
4. Should be aware of the social media platforms or accounts used by Rhand Rhelle;
5. Should give their consent upon participating in the study.

In order to alleviate any involvement of vulnerability in this study, the population of the study only included Rhand Rhelle sneakerheads aged 18 to 64, which is elusive of vulnerable age groups such as children, the elderly, ethnic and racial minorities groups, and others. Therefore, any grounds violating these criteria could result in disqualification from participating in the study.

Sampling Procedure

A random sampling technique was utilized in choosing the 100 participants in this study. According to Simkus (2022), in performing this sampling method, every individual who is part of a population is given an equal opportunity to be chosen through an objective selection method. A random method was used to choose the sample after assigning a number to each participant in the sample population. Further, due to the unknown total population, the researcher decided to have a target number

of 100 participants. This sample size was computed using the G Power software, an operating system that is usually utilized in determining the sample size when the population is unknown.

Data Gathering Procedure

Tasks	Aug – Sept 2022	Oct – Nov 2022	Dec 2022 – Feb 2023	Mar – Apr 2023	May 2023	Jun – Jul 2023	Aug – Sept 2023
Preparation of Research Proposal							
Submission of Research Proposal							
Presentation of Research Proposal							
Data Collection							
Data Analysis							
Research Paper Writing							
Finalizing Research Paper							
Submission of Research Paper							
Presentation of Research Paper							

Figure 3. Gantt Chart of Research Timeline and Activities

Figure 3 shows the timeline of the various steps that the researcher conducted in this study. The research proposal was finished from August 2022 until September 2022, the last trimester for the academic year 2022-2023. The researcher presented the study's proposal from October 2022 until February 2023, the span of the first trimester of the academic year 2022-2023. The researcher administered the data collection and analysis from March 2023 until May 2023. Lastly, the researcher performed the research paper writing up to the research paper's presentation from June 2023 until September 2023.

The researcher used online survey questionnaires, which comprised four sections:

1. Section 1 briefly explains the study, its purpose, its significance to the participants, and the consent form.
2. Section 2 consists of demographic questions such as name (optional), age, sex, and the inclusion criteria the respondents should possess.

3. Section 3 encompasses questions based on the study's objectives, namely:
 - a. The attitudes and perceptions of sneakerheads regarding social media usage and social media marketing;
 - b. Significant factors in making social media marketing effective on sneakerheads, particularly on customer loyalty and purchase decisions;
 - c. And how sneaker businesses can utilize social media to improve customer interaction.
4. Lastly, section 4 extends gratitude to the participants and the announcement on the release of winners regarding the e-gift certificates.

For sections 2 and 3, the researcher adopted and modified the survey questionnaire developed by Gibson (2018) in his study entitled "An Analysis of the Impact of Social Media Marketing on Individuals' Attitudes and Perceptions at NOVA Community College" to determine how social media marketing can affect sneakerhead's perceptions and purchasing decisions. Gibson's questionnaire has two parts: Part 1 of the questionnaire is about the demographic characteristics of the participants, while Part 2 focuses on the participants' attitudes and perceptions toward sneaker businesses using social media marketing. Additionally, this instrument was validated by three professionals as follows: (a) a research adviser, (b) a technical critic, and (c) a business or marketing professional that played as an external validator. Thus, the questionnaire was revised in accordance with the recommendations of these validators.

The researcher was forthcoming about how participant data were utilized in the study. The participants were briefed prior to the start of the survey and were not misled. During this briefing, the researcher addressed the protection of the participant's privacy and confidentiality by quick access and password-protected restricted access

to the forms containing their information, particularly in accordance with the Data Privacy Act or R.A. No. 10173:

1. Participants' right to change or access their information;
2. Participants' right for their data to be held securely and shall not be distributed to third parties;
3. Participants' right for their data to be disposed of under official university procedure once information is no longer required.

The only individuals with access to the files will be the researcher and the research advisor.

The researcher disseminated the online survey questionnaires during data collection using Google Forms. The researcher presented a consent form in section 1 of the online survey questionnaire to reassure the participants that all answers shall remain confidential and that their responses were treated with the utmost discretion. Furthermore, applying the principle of respect for persons in research ethics, the researcher ensured that the participants understood that participating is voluntary, they have the right not to participate in the study, and that declining would not affect their overall well-being.

The participants have the option to withdraw at any time if they feel uneasy while answering the survey questionnaire or if they have experienced extraordinary circumstances that prohibit their participation. Moreover, the researchers shall notify the participants that they can ask any question regarding the study to ascertain the participants' safety and suppress possible risks. Since the study involves an individual's behavior, questions may be too personal, sensitive, or confidential. Therefore, there could be a risk of embarrassment, discomfort, or fear upon answering the survey. Nonetheless, the researcher shall guarantee that the participants will not

be harmed and exposed to exploitation during the data-gathering process. Also, the researcher will perform their best to minimize the risks and harms that may indulge the participants.

In order to gather a higher response rate, the researcher planned to collaborate with Rhand Rhelle to distribute six ₱500 e-gift certificates to random participants. The duration of their participation only took at most 10 minutes of their time, dependent on their pace. The researcher sponsored the funding sources for this study.

The participants read and typed their responses to complete the online questionnaire. Invasive or unsuitable topics that might provoke unfavorable replies will not be included in the survey form. The researcher did not disseminate the survey's findings in any manner nor release any personal information or questionnaire replies. Moreover, the participants were not compelled to answer personal or unsettling questions.

The participants did not receive any pay or incentives beyond reimbursements for expenses that may have been sustained as a result of participating in this study. Conversely, aside from the e-gift certificates (self-funded by the researcher) that some participants can acquire, there were no direct advantages and impacts linked with participating in this research study. However, the data extracted may enable the researcher to grasp the relationships between the investigated variables, which may further benefit the academe and businesses, particularly Rhand Rhelle, in the future.

As stated previously, the only individuals with access to the obtained data are the researcher and the research adviser who participated in the data analysis. In addition, the participant was not identified or directed in the data presented. The researcher then will dispose of the data gathered once the minimum retention period of 5 years has passed and if the data is no longer of value or meets ethical

requirements (University of Tasmania - Library, 2022). However, the researcher may need to keep the data collected for the long term or permanently, depending on the research outcome. As the researcher sponsored the finances for this study, the researcher certified that they have no affiliations with or involvement in any organization or entity with any financial or non-financial interest in the subject matter or materials discussed in this manuscript.

The researcher has obtained a certificate from the Panel on Research Ethics from completing the Course on Research Ethics based on the Tri-Council Policy Statement: Ethical Conduct for Research Involving Humans (TCPS 2: CORE 2022). Therefore, the researcher reaffirmed to comply with all research ethics directives – that all information and data that were included in this study are true, accurate, complete, and reliable. Moreover, the researcher also understood the act of plagiarism, which would diminish the researcher's efforts if such an issue shall be detected. Hence, the researcher abode by the laws and regulations and certify the study's originality.

Data Analysis

The researcher obtained the results of the study from the figures presented in the summary of responses in Google Forms. These results were tabulated and subjected to statistical treatment using simple frequency count, percentage, and weighted Mean. For proper presentation, the data were converted to pie charts.

Frequency and percentage were used for the demographic profile and survey responses of the participants.

Formula:

$$\% = \frac{F}{N} \times 100$$

Where:

% = percentage

f = frequency

N = total number of participants

Weighted Mean was used to compute the average.

Formula:

$$\bar{X} = \frac{\sum X}{n}$$

Where:

\bar{X} = mean of the set of x values

$\sum x$ = summation of weighted Mean

n = number of responses

Standard Deviation was used to determine how close the variation of the results.

Formula:

$$s = \sqrt{\frac{\sum(x - \bar{x})^2}{n - 1}}$$

Where:

σ = Standard Deviation

X_i = Terms are given in the data

n = Total number of terms

X = Mean of the data

To ensure that there were no inappropriate responses, the researcher made use of Response Validation, a feature in Google Forms. It is a set of rules that restrict the responses of the participants upon filling out the online questionnaire. Furthermore, the researcher also analyzed the summary of responses downloaded in Microsoft Excel to certify the completeness and accuracy of the data.

The responses were analyzed to uncover significant factors that affect sneakerheads' social behavior toward social media marketing. The study utilized descriptive analysis to understand the influence of social media marketing on the attitudes and perceptions of sneakerheads.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Presented in this part of the paper are the gathered and analyzed data that sufficed the research objectives, which are as follows: (a) determine the attitudes and perceptions of respondents in terms of social media usage and social media marketing; (b) assess the significant factors in making social media marketing effective on sneakerheads, particularly on customer brand loyalty and purchase decisions; and (c) identify how sneaker businesses can utilize social media to improve customer interaction. In addition, the initial target respondents of the study were 100; however, the researcher was able to acquire 120 responses. Thus, the additional twenty (20) respondents were included in the analysis of data, which was deemed better as outliers can be potentially managed.

Demographic Profile of Respondents

Although not the center of the study, the demographic profile of the respondents assisted the researcher in yielding further implications of the research findings. In addition, these data may potentially be utilized by future researchers who are interested in investigating factors related to the demographic profile of sneakerheads.

Table 1. Age of the Respondents

Age	Frequency	Percentage
18-20	3	3%
21-30	90	75%
31-40	22	18%
41-50	4	3%
51-60	1	1%
TOTAL	120	100%

The table above presents the data regarding the age of the respondents. As shown, the respondents who are 21 to 30 years old comprised the highest percentage of the sample size, which is 75%. On the other hand, the least percentage of the sample size belongs to the age bracket of 51 to 60 years old. These data may infer that most of the sneakerheads who purchase shoes at Rhand Rhelle are mostly in their young adulthood. However, there are still consumers, even if they are few, in their middle adulthood.

Table 2. Sex of the Respondents

Sex	Frequency	Percentage
Male	79	66%
Female	39	32%
Unknown	2	2%
TOTAL	120	100

Table 2 revealed the data regarding the sex of the respondents. As presented, the sneakerheads are dominantly identified as males (66%). Meanwhile, there are still female sneakerheads (32%) who purchase in Rhand Rhelle. However, there were two participants who chose not to disclose their sex, which was respected by the research. Nevertheless, the data may infer that more than half of sneakerheads who purchase Rhand Rhelle are males, but there are also numerous female consumers.

Table 3. Consumer Profile of Sneakerheads

Profile	Yes	%	No	%
Owned a Social Media Account (Facebook, Instagram, YouTube, etc.)	120	100%	0	0
Awareness of Social Media Accounts of Rhand Rhelle	120	100%	0	0
Purchase of Rhand Rhelle Products and Services	120	100%	0	0

The table above presents the consumer profile of the respondents. It revealed that all of the respondents owned social media accounts, such as Facebook, Instagram, YouTube, etc. Also, all of the respondents are aware of the social media accounts of Rhand Rhelle. Lastly, all of the respondents already purchased products or availed of the services of the mentioned sneaker business. These data may infer that all of the respondents passed the inclusion criteria of the study as they were sneakerheads who were on social media and consumers of Rhand Rhelle.

Attitudes and Perceptions of Sneakerheads

Social Media Usage

Figure 4. Number of Social Media Platforms Used for Buy and Sell of Sneakers

Shown in the figure above is the data regarding the social media usage of the respondents, specific to the number of social media platforms utilized by the respondents for sneaker buying and selling. As revealed, more than half of the respondents (59.2%) utilize at least two (2) platforms. On the other hand, the least percentage of respondents are revealed to utilize one (1) social media platform. Therefore, sellers and buyers of sneakers are more likely to use at least two (2) platforms, which can be due to higher audience reach or more choices of sneaker products.

Figure 5. Social Media Platforms Used by Respondents

The figure above presents the data regarding the social media platforms used by the sneakerheads. As shown, Facebook garnered the highest frequency of respondents, which was 78. However, Instagram, with 71 sneakerheads, was the second most utilized social media platform. On the other hand, there were also respondents who were using other social media platforms other than Facebook, Twitter, and Instagram. This data may infer that most sneakerheads are using Facebook, while Instagram is the secondary platform they usually utilize.

Figure 6. Frequency of Social Media Engagement as a Sneakerhead

Presented in the figure above is the data presenting the frequency of social media engagement of respondents as sneakerheads per week. As revealed, most respondents usually engage in social media as sneaker enthusiasts at least three times a week (48.3%). On the other hand, the least percentage of respondents rarely engaged (4.2%), while there were no respondents who ever engaged in social media as sneakerheads. Therefore, the respondents always engage in social media as sneakerheads, and the frequency only varies, whereas most of them use social media due to the mentioned characteristic frequently.

Figure 7. Time Spent Browsing Sneaker-Related Posts on Social Media

Figure 7 reveals the daily time spent by the respondents browsing sneaker-related posts on social media platforms that they use. As presented, more than half of the sneakerheads (52.5%) spend 30 minutes to an hour browsing sneaker-related posts. On the other hand, the least percentage of the respondents (8.3%) revealed to only spend less than 30 minutes browsing the mentioned social media content. These data may infer that most respondents consciously or unconsciously allot 30 minutes to an hour of their day browsing sneaker-related posts on social media.

Social Media Marketing

Figure 8. Effect of Social Media Marketing of an Online Sneaker Store on Sneakerheads' Purchase

The figure disclosed the data on the effect of social media marketing of an online sneaker store on sneakerheads' purchases. Most respondents believed that the social media marketing of online sneaker stores could affect how they purchase (81.7%). However, there were also 18.3% of the respondents who do not think that social media marketing affects how they purchase. Nevertheless, the data infer that most respondents are aware that social media marketing affects their purchase behavior.

Impacts of Social Media Marketing among Sneakerheads

Customer Brand Loyalty and Purchase Decisions

Table 4. Important Factors for a Business Using Social Media

Variables	Rating Responses					N	Mean Rating	Standard Deviation
	Most Important		3	Least Important				
	1	2		4	5			
Consistency of posts	30	30	19	32	9	120	2.67	1.31
Type of content posted	30	42	25	15	8	120	2.41	1.84
Customer engagement	18	24	44	15	19	120	2.94	1.25
Online promotions	23	15	18	40	24	120	3.23	1.41
Timing of Posts	19	9	14	18	60	120	3.76	1.52

The respondents were asked to rate the factors presented above in terms of their importance for a business using social media, where one reflects being the most important while five means the least important. As presented above, the factor

regarding the type of content posted by the business was rated to be the most important factor as it has the smallest Mean of 2.41, which means that numerous respondents rated it as the most important (1 or 2). On the other hand, the timing of the post was deemed to be the least important factor as it was revealed to have the highest Mean of 3.75, which means the numerous respondents rated it as least important (4 or 5).

Figure 9. Perception of Sneakerheads in Increased Profits Due to Customer Loyalty from Social Media Marketing Integration

The figure revealed the data regarding the perception of sneakerheads in increased profits due to customer loyalty from social media marketing integration. As revealed, 99.2% of the respondents believed that the profits of businesses could increase due to customer loyalty that resulted from the integration of social media in marketing. On the other hand, only 0.8% of the respondents believed otherwise. Therefore, almost all of the respondents believed that customer loyalty could be acquired by businesses through social media marketing, which may further result to increases profits.

Figure 10. Perception of Sneakerheads in Utility of Social Media Reach to Target Audience

As revealed by Figure 10, most of the respondents (95%) perceived that through social media, businesses are able to reach their target audience, which is the sneakerheads. This data can be deemed consistent with the presented data above that involves all the respondents having social media accounts and being aware of the accounts used by Rhand Rhelle and also with the findings revealing their frequent browsing in social media. On the other hand, only 5% of the respondents perceived otherwise. These data may infer that social media is perceived to be a useful tool for businesses to reach their target audiences.

Utility of Social Media to Improve Customer Interaction

Figure 11. Percentage of Updated Sneakerheads in Terms of Sneaker Promotions

Figure 11 reveals the data regarding the percentage of respondents who are updated in terms of sneaker promotions that are posted on social media. As revealed, most respondents (91.7%) are updated to the mentioned type of promotion, while only 8.3% revealed that they were not updated. Therefore, most sneakerheads are updated with the promotions, which can be due to their frequent browsing and following the social media account of the sneaker business.

Figure 12. Percentage of Sneakerheads Availing Sneaker Promotions on Social Media

The figure revealed the percentage of sneakerheads availing of sneaker promotions on social media. As presented, 94.2% of the respondents availed of sneaker promotions that they saw on social media. On the other hand, only 5.8% did not take advantage of the promotions posted on social media. Therefore, most respondents are more likely to take advantage of sneaker promotions on social media.

Figure 13. Percentage of Sneakerheads Posting Experiences in Sneaker Business on Social Media

Figure 13 presents the percentage of sneakerheads who are more likely to post their experiences in the sneaker business on social media. As revealed, 52.5% of the respondents are more likely to post their experiences with the sneaker business on social media. On the other hand, only 4.2% revealed that they are not likely to post their experiences on social media involving the sneaker business. These data may infer that sneakerheads are more likely to provide their feedback on social media, which can be crucial in the social media marketing of businesses.

Figure 14. Percentage of Sneakerheads who Repost, Re-story, and Retweet Sneaker Sale or Promotion Codes to Friends on Social Media

Presented in the figure above is the percentage of respondents who report, re-story, and retweet sneaker sales or promotion codes among their friends on social media. As revealed, more than half of the respondents (63.3%) are very likely to repost, re-story, and retweet sales and promotions of sneaker business among their friends on social media. On the other hand, only 2.5% of the respondents revealed to undertake the otherwise. This data may infer that most sneakerheads will post their feedback on social media, which can either threaten or enhance social media marketing depending on whether the experience was pleasant or not.

V. SUMMARY, CONCLUSION, AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Summary and Conclusion

The sneakerheads are revealed to be mostly male, ages 21 to 30, owned a social media account, were aware of the social media accounts of Rhand Rhelle, and are consumers of the mentioned sneaker business; therefore, it can be concluded that most sneakers at Rhand Rhelle are purchased by male customers who are young adults and have access to them in social media.

Moreover, in terms of the attitudes and perceptions of sneakerheads, it was revealed that sneakerheads are more likely to use at least two social media accounts for sneaker buying and selling, Facebook, engage in social media as a sneakerhead at least three times a week and browse sneaker-related posts in social media at least 30 minutes to an hour. Therefore, the researcher concluded that sneakerheads are active social media users, especially on Facebook, which was the most utilized social media platform of the respondents. In addition, it can be concluded that sneakerheads have a positive attitude towards social media, considering their patronage and engagement on it. In line with this, the respondents are revealed to perceive social media marketing of online sneaker stores as an effective factor influencing their purchase behavior. Therefore, the respondents perceive that online sneaker stores can benefit from social media marketing.

Moving forward to the significant factors in making social media marketing effective on sneakerheads, particularly on customer brand loyalty and purchase decisions, there were three significant findings revealed. First, the type of content posted by online sneaker businesses was revealed to be the most important factor for businesses to consider as they utilize social media. Therefore, as sneakerheads are

the target audience, sneaker businesses should ensure that the content of their posts is about sneakers, which can attract the attention and interests of the respondents. It is crucial that the content posted is aligned with the needs and interests of the target consumers. Second, the respondents revealed that perceived customer loyalty could be acquired by businesses through social media marketing, which may further result to increases profits. Therefore, social media marketing can create potential business outcomes, where one of them is customer loyalty, which can be linked to higher profits. Lastly, social media was perceived by the sneakerheads to be a useful tool for businesses to reach their target audiences. Therefore, if sneaker businesses aim to reach more audiences, they can strengthen their online presence.

Meanwhile, in the findings regarding the utility of social media in improving customer interaction, there were four revealed findings. First, it was revealed that most sneakerheads are updated with sneaker promotions that they became aware of because of social media. Therefore, sneakerheads can be motivated to browse sneaker-related content in the mentioned platform in pursuit of being aware of when there are promotions. In line with this, most respondents are revealed to avail of sneaker promotions on social media. Therefore, as sneakerheads browse social media, they not only get updated with promotions, but they actually take advantage of them. Moreover, the findings revealed that most sneakerheads post their experiences on social media. Therefore, sneakerheads are crucial in the social media marketing of online businesses, especially in their brand image. Lastly, the findings revealed that most sneakerheads are very likely to repost, re-story, and retweet sales and promotions of sneaker businesses among their friends on social media. Therefore, sneakerheads play an important role in online sneaker stores to further widen their audience reach.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusions, the researcher recommends the following. First, Rhand Rhelle may sell sneakers that are suitable for the demographics of its consumers. They may have more stocks of sneakers that are more likely to appeal to males and young adults.

Moreover, the researcher recommends sneaker businesses utilize different social media platforms that are frequently utilized by sneakerheads, such as Facebook and Instagram. Although sneaker businesses may focus on one platform, recommended to be Facebook as it was the most frequently used, it is advisable to still create another business account on another platform to widen audience reach. In addition, active usage of social media marketing can be recommended, as sneakerheads are frequently browsing sneaker-related posts. In line with this, sneaker businesses may try to avail paid advertisements on Facebook for them to be more visible among users who are interested in sneakers. Lastly, either a social media marketer can be hired, or the owners may further enrich their knowledge and skills in terms of social media marketing. In this case, they may potentially maximize social media as a platform for their business.

Furthermore, aspiring and present sneaker business owners are recommended to consider the type of content that they will intend to post on their social media business accounts. They are recommended to ensure that the contents are appealing and can spark interest among sneakerheads. In line with this, they may enhance the quality of the photos of their products while still maintaining their authentic form. Additionally, if sneaker businesses aim to have loyal consumers, it is crucial for them to enhance their social media marketing. Thus, it can be recommended that these businesses can involve loyal customer perks in their social media marketing strategy.

Similar to the recommendation above, these businesses may invest in social media advertising or hire experts in the field to increase loyalty and profit.

Lastly, the researcher recommends a strengthened and strategic creation of promotions and merit systems in social media. The promotions may entail discounts, packages, and limited-time offers. In this way, businesses can motivate sneakerheads to purchase their products. In addition, a merit system may involve giving perks or rewards to account followers who actively engage with their posts, such as reacting, commenting, sharing, retweeting, re-story, and reposting. Also, when consumers have reached a certain amount or frequency of purchase, a discount can be given.

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Appendices

APPENDIX A

Survey Matrix

Cop or Drop: An Analysis of the Influence of Social Media Marketing on Sneakerheads' Attitudes and Perceptions Among Resellers and Consumers of Rhand Rhelle <i>Survey Matrix</i>		
Objectives	What data do I need?	Questions
Determine the attitudes and perceptions of sneakerheads regarding social media usage and social media marketing.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Social media usage of sneakerheads ● Sneakerheads' impression on social media marketing 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. How many social media sites do you use for buying and/or selling sneakers? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● 1 ● 2 ● 3 ● More than 3 2. What social media sites and services do you regularly use for buying and/or selling sneakers? (Check all that apply) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Facebook Twitter Instagram Other 3. How often do you engage in social media as a sneakerhead? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Everyday ● Three times a week ● Once a week ● Rarely ● Never 4. How much time do you spend browsing for sneaker-related posts on social media? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Less than 30 minutes

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● 30 minutes to an hour ● 1-2 hours ● 3 or more hours <p>5. As a customer, does the social media marketing of an online sneaker store affect your purchase?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Yes ● No
<p>Assess the significant factors in making social media marketing effective on sneakerheads, particularly on customer brand loyalty and purchase decisions.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Sneakerheads' opinion on what significant factors make social media marketing effective ● Sneakerheads' perception regarding the effectiveness of integrating social media marketing on customer brand loyalty and purchase decisions 	<p>6. In your own opinion, what are the important factors for a sneaker business using social media marketing? Rate each factor by importance, with 1 being the most important and 5 being the least important.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Consistency of posts ● Type of content posted ● Customer engagement (i.e. customer service) ● Online promotions ● Timing of posts <p>7. Do you believe that sneaker businesses will profit more and achieve better results when it comes to customer loyalty if social media is integrated into marketing?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Yes ● No <p>8. Do you believe social media is the best way to reach a sneaker business' targeted audience?</p>

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Yes ● No
Identify how sneaker businesses can utilize social media to improve customer interaction.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Social media activities of the sneakerheads ● Social media experience of the sneakerheads 	<p>9. Are you up to date with sneaker promotions (e.g., sale or discounts) using social media?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Yes ● No <p>10. Have you ever taken advantage of a sneaker promotion (e.g., sale or discounts) you heard about via social media?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Yes ● No <p>11. How likely are you to post about your experience with a sneaker business on social media?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Very likely ● Somewhat likely ● Not likely <p>12. How likely would you repost, re-story, or retweet a sneaker sale or promotion code to your friends on social media?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Very likely ● Somewhat likely ● Not likely

APPENDIX B

Survey Questionnaire

Cop or Drop: An Analysis of the Influence of Social Media Marketing on Sneakerheads' Attitudes and Perceptions Among Resellers and Consumers of Rhand Rhelle

Section I: Introduction

Good day!

I am Krizia Anne S. Estrella, a 4th year BA Multimedia Studies student from the University of the Philippines Open University. I am currently conducting undergraduate research entitled "Cop or Drop: An Analysis of the Influence of Social Media Marketing on Sneakerheads' Attitudes and Perceptions Among Resellers and Consumers of Rhand Rhelle." By definition, a **sneakerhead** can either be a collector, consumer, or reseller in the sneaker market.

My study aims to analyze the influence of social media marketing on sneakerheads' attitudes and perceptions. In particular, this study aims to answer the questions:

1. *What are the attitudes and perceptions of sneakerheads regarding social media usage and social media marketing?*
2. *What are the significant factors that make social media marketing effective on sneakerheads, particularly on customer brand loyalty and purchase decisions?*
3. *How can sneaker businesses utilize social media to improve customer interaction?*

The survey will consist of two parts. Part 1 of the questionnaire is about the demographic characteristics of the participants. While part 2 focuses on sneakerheads' attitudes and perceptions toward sneaker businesses using social media marketing.

Answering this survey would only take **at most 10 minutes** of your time. You will not be harmed or exposed to discrimination upon answering this survey. There are no personal or unsettling questions included. You can also ask any questions regarding the study upon completing the survey. Rest assured that answering this survey is **completely voluntary**. You may withdraw from answering the survey at any point. Declining or withdrawing from participating in this study will not involve any penalty.

By answering this survey, not only will you help me fulfill my undergraduate research, but you will also be helping the field of multimedia research. Furthermore, you will have the chance to win a **₱500 e-gift-certificate** consumable in Rhand Rhelle!

Please do not hesitate to contact me through my email at ksestrella@up.edu.ph or contact 09190986739 if you have any questions or concerns.

Thank you very much!

Note: This survey will require an email address for the ₱500 e-gift-certificates that will be distributed to random participants.

Section II: Consent Form

In answering this form, I agree to my data being used to contribute to the researcher's multimedia study on:

Cop or Drop: An Analysis of the Influence of Social Media Marketing on Sneakerheads' Attitudes and Perceptions Among Resellers and Consumers of Rhand Rhelle

The information will only be accessed by the researcher and the research adviser in this study. I understand my data will be held securely and will not be distributed to third parties. I have the right to change or access my information. I know that when this information is no longer required for this purpose, an official university procedure will be followed to dispose of my data in compliance with the Data Privacy Act (R.A. No. 10173).

Do you give your consent to participate in this survey?

- Yes, I agree to participate in this survey and share my data.
- No, I disagree to participate in this survey and won't share my data.

Section III: Demographics

Name (Optional):

Age (numbers between 18 and 64):

Sex (female, male, prefer not to say):

Do you have a social media account? (Facebook, Instagram, YouTube, etc.)

- Yes
- No

Are you aware of the social media platforms or accounts used by Rhand Rhelle?

- Yes
- No

Have you purchased a product or availed of any services of Rhand Rhelle at least once?

- Yes
- No

Section IV: *The following questions are adopted and modified from Gibson's (2018) questionnaire on his study entitled: An Analysis of the Impact of Social Media Marketing on Individuals' Attitudes and Perceptions at NOVA Community College.*

1. How many social media sites do you use for buying and/or selling sneakers?

- 1

- 2
 - 3
 - More than 3
2. What social media sites and services do you regularly use for buying and/or selling sneakers? (Check all that apply)
- Facebook
 - Twitter
 - Instagram
 - Other
3. How often do you engage in social media as a sneakerhead?
- Everyday
 - Three times a week
 - Once a week
 - Rarely
 - Never
4. How much time do you spend browsing for sneaker-related posts on social media?
- Less than 30 minutes
 - 30 minutes to an hour
 - 1-2 hours
 - 3 or more hours
5. As a customer, does the social media marketing of an online sneaker store affect your purchase?
- Yes
 - No
6. In your own opinion, what are the important factors for a sneaker business using social media marketing? Rate each factor by importance, with 1 being the most important and 5 being the least important.
- | | | | | | |
|---|---|---|---|---|---|
| | 1 | 2 | 3 | 4 | 5 |
| Consistency of posts | | | | | |
| Type of content posted | | | | | |
| Customer engagement (i.e. customer service) | | | | | |
| Online promotions | | | | | |
| Timing of posts | | | | | |
7. Do you believe that sneaker businesses will profit more and achieve better results when it comes to customer loyalty if social media is integrated into marketing?
- Yes

- No
8. Do you believe that social media is the best way to reach a sneaker business' targeted audience?
- Yes
 - No
9. Are you up to date with sneaker promotions (e.g., sale or discounts) by using social media?
- Yes
 - No
10. Have you ever taken advantage of a sneaker promotion (e.g., sale or discounts) you heard about via social media?
- Yes
 - No
11. How likely are you to post about your experience with a sneaker business on social media?
- Very likely
 - Somewhat likely
 - Not likely
12. How likely would you repost, re-story, or retweet a sneaker sale or promotion code to your friends on social media?
- Very likely
 - Somewhat likely
 - Not likely

Section V: Thank you so much for participating in this survey!

We will announce the release of winners regarding the e-gift certificates on Rhand Rhelle's social media accounts. Winners shall receive an email containing the ₱500 e-gift-certificate consumable in Rhand Rhelle.

I thank you for your continuous support. If you have encountered any problems while answering this survey or have questions, you may email me at ksestrella@up.edu.ph or contact 09190986739. I'd gladly accommodate you. Once again, thank you so much, and I sincerely hope you and your loved ones are safe.

APPENDIX C

Google Form

Cop or Drop: An Analysis of the Influence of Social Media Marketing on Sneakerheads' Attitudes and Perceptions Among Resellers and Consumers of Rhand Rhelle

Good day!

I am Krizia Anne S. Estrella, a 4th year BA Multimedia Studies student from the University of the Philippines Open University. I am currently conducting undergraduate research entitled "Cop or Drop: An Analysis of the Influence of Social Media Marketing on Sneakerheads' Attitudes and Perceptions Among Resellers and Consumers of Rhand Rhelle." By definition, a **sneakerhead** can either be a collector, consumer, or reseller in the sneaker market.

My study aims to analyze the influence of social media marketing on sneakerheads' attitudes and perceptions. In particular, this study aims to answer the questions:

1. *What are the attitudes and perceptions of sneakerheads regarding social media usage and social media marketing?*
2. *What are the significant factors that make social media marketing effective on sneakerheads, particularly on customer brand loyalty and purchase decisions?*
3. *How can sneaker businesses utilize social media to improve customer interaction?*

The survey will consist of two parts. Part 1 of the questionnaire is about the demographic characteristics of the participants. While part 2 focuses on sneakerheads' attitudes and perceptions toward sneaker businesses using social media marketing.

Answering this survey would only take **at most 10 minutes** of your time. You will not be harmed or exposed to discrimination upon answering this survey. There are no personal or unsettling questions included. You can also ask any questions regarding the study upon completing the survey. Rest assured that answering this survey is **completely voluntary**. You may withdraw from answering the survey at any point. Declining or withdrawing from participating in this study will not involve any penalty.

By answering this survey, not only will you help me fulfill my undergraduate research, but you will also be helping the field of multimedia research. Furthermore, you will have the chance to win a **₱500 e-gift certificate** consumable in Rhand Rhelle!

Please do not hesitate to contact me through my email at ksestrella@up.edu.ph or contact 09190986739 if you have any questions or concerns.

Thank you very much!

Note: This survey will require an email address for the ₱500 e-gift certificates that will be distributed to random participants.

* Indicates required question

Email *

Cannot pre-fill email

Consent Form

In answering this form, I agree to my data being used to contribute to the researcher's multimedia study on:

Cop or Drop: An Analysis of the Influence of Social Media Marketing on Sneakerheads' Attitudes and Perceptions Among Resellers and Consumers of Rhand Rhelle

The information will only be accessed by the researcher and the research adviser in this study. I understand my data will be held securely and will not be distributed to third parties. I have the right to change or access my information. I know that when this information is no longer required for this purpose, an official university procedure will be followed to dispose of my data in compliance with the Data Privacy Act (R.A. No. 10173).

Do you give your consent to participate in this survey? *

- Yes, I agree to participate in this survey and share my data.
- No, I disagree to participate in this survey and won't share my data.

Demographics

Name (Optional)

Your answer

Age *

Your answer

Sex

- Male
- Female
- Prefer not to say

Do you have a social media account? (Facebook, Instagram, YouTube, etc.) *

- Yes
- No

Are you aware of the social media platforms or accounts used by Rhand Rhelle? *

- Yes
- No

Have you purchased a product or availed of any services of Rhand Rhelle at least once? *

- Yes
- No

Questionnaire

*The following questions are adopted and modified from [Gibson's \(2018\)](#) questionnaire on his study entitled: *An Analysis of the Impact of Social Media Marketing on Individuals' Attitudes and Perceptions at NOVA Community College*.*

1. How many social media sites do you use for buying and/or selling sneakers? *

- 1
- 2
- 3
- More than 3

2. What social media sites and services do you regularly use for buying and/or selling sneakers? (Check all that apply) *

- Facebook
- Twitter

- Instagram
- Other

3. How often do you engage in social media as a sneakerhead? *

- Everyday
- Three times a week
- Once a week
- Rarely
- Never

4. How much time do you spend browsing for sneaker-related posts on social media? *

- Less than 30 minutes
- 30 minutes to an hour
- 1-2 hours
- 3 or more hours

5. As a customer, does the social media marketing of an online sneaker store affect your purchase? *

- Yes
- No

6. In your own opinion, what are the important factors for a sneaker business using social media marketing? Rate each factor by importance, with 1 being the most important and 5 being the least important. *

	1	2	3	4	5
Consistency of posts	<input type="radio"/>				
Type of content posted	<input type="radio"/>				

Customer
engagement
(i.e. customer

10. Have you ever taken advantage of a sneaker promotion (e.g., sale or discounts) you heard about via social media? *

- Yes
- No

11. How likely are you to post about your experience with a sneaker business on social media? *

- Very likely
- Somewhat likely
- Not likely

12. How likely would you repost, re-story, or retweet a sneaker sale or promotion code to your friends on social media? *

- Very likely
- Somewhat likely
- Not likely

Thank you so much for participating in this survey!

We will announce the release of winners regarding the e-gift certificates on Rhand Rhelle's social media accounts. Winners shall receive an email containing the ₱500 e-gift certificate consumable in Rhand Rhelle.

I thank you for your continuous support. If you have encountered any problems while answering this survey or have questions, you may email me at ksestrella@up.edu.ph or contact 09190986739. I'd gladly accommodate you. Once again, thank you so much, and I sincerely hope you and your loved ones are safe.

11. How likely are you to post about your experience with a sneaker business on social media? *

APPENDIX D

Certificate from the Panel on Research Ethics

APPENDIX E

Documentation during Data Gathering

